

On the Photochemical Reaction between Glucose and Hydrogen Peroxide in Acid Medium with Tungstic Acid Sol as Photocatalyst. Part I.

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In a previous communication from this laboratory Kappanna (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 387) has shown that the oxidation of glucose by iodine depends essentially on the p_H of the medium, and that phosphates regulate the oxidation of glucose only by their action as buffering agents. In the present paper, results of further study on the oxidation of glucose are presented.

It is well known that the reaction between glucose and hydrogen peroxide proceeds quickly in the dark in an alkaline medium but in an acid solution, the velocity of oxidation of glucose by hydrogen peroxide even at 40° is almost negligible (Harden and Henley, *Biochem. J.*, 1921, 15, 672). This oxidation of glucose by hydrogen peroxide has not been found to be at all sensitive to light. In the presence of tungstic acid sol the rate of oxidation of glucose by hydrogen peroxide is also negligible in the dark, but if the reaction mixture is exposed to radiations in the immediate ultraviolet, the oxidation has been found to proceed with considerable velocity.

Qualitative observations on the photochemical reduction of tungstic acid by celluloses, sugar, glucose, dextrin, etc., have already been made by various investigators.

Sabanejeff found that when sodium metawolframate was treated with excess of hydrochloric acid and dialysed, the sol consisted of particles having the composition $Na_2O, 4WO_3, 2H_2O$. It is curious however that the sol when freshly prepared can reduce grape sugar in presence of light. Whereas on ageing, it ceases to be photosensitive. Wassiljewa (*Z. wiss. Phot.*, 1913, 12, 1) studied thoroughly this phenomenon of ageing of tungstic acid sol. The velocity of reduction of tungstic acid sol by excess of glucose in presence of radiations from a constant source of light was determined by titrating

the reduced blue compound of tungsten with standard permanganate solution. Wassiljewa assumed that the rate of reduction at any time was a measure of the concentration of photo-sensitive tungstic acid sol present at that time. He concluded that the velocity of transformation of tungstic acid sol from the photosensitive to the photo-insensitive variety followed the unimolecular equation, and he suggests that on ageing, the sol gains in hydration, thus:—

It has been observed by the authors, in course of the present investigation, that with excess of glucose, the photochemical reduction of tungstic acid does not proceed to completion, but that depending on the intensity of light the reaction comes to a stop after a certain amount of reduced tungsten compound has been formed. In our investigation the concentration of the reduced blue compound never exceeded an equivalent of $M/150$ potassium permanganate. But if, after the reaction had been brought to a standstill, the light from the mercury lamp was cut off, and a stream of air bubbled through the reduced solution in the quartz tube, until the blue colour disappeared, and then the mixture again exposed to light, the reduction progressed as rapidly as before. Very probably, the cause of this reaction being brought to a stop is to be sought for in the screening effect of the coloured substance from the active radiations. This phenomenon of auto-retardation throws doubt on the validity of the assumption of Wassiljewa that the rate of reduction is a measure of the concentration of the photosensitive sol.

During the process of the photochemical oxidation of glucose by hydrogen peroxide in presence of tungstic acid, the appearance of this blue colour could not be noticed, indicating that the reduced blue compound of tungsten was not formed at all, or that it disappeared as soon as it was formed. The complicated phenomenon of auto-retardation, which is closely associated with the concentration of the reduced blue compound of tungsten, was therefore entirely eliminated in our investigation, and tungstic acid sol behaved as a pure photocatalyst in the oxidation of glucose by hydrogen peroxide. The disturbing effect due to the ageing and the consequent desensitization of the sol is not very perceptible within four hours of the preparation of the sol; and hence all measurements of reaction velocity recorded in this paper were completed within four hours after the preparation of the reaction mixture.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The source of light was a quartz mercury-lamp run at constant values of current and voltage from a storage battery. The reaction mixture was kept inside a quartz tube placed at a constant distance from the light source. The temperature of the mixture was kept constant by enclosing the reaction tube inside a larger quartz tube, the annular space being filled with water which was circulated from a thermostat by means of a pump.

Corning glass filter G. 586 (*vide* Technologic papers of the Bureau of Standards, No. 148) was used for isolating the spectral region 330-430 $\mu\mu$ in the violet and the ultraviolet. These radiations have no action on hydrogen peroxide as such, but the ultraviolet light transmitted by this filter is very effective in bringing about the oxidation of glucose by tungstic acid sol and hydrogen peroxide.

The reaction mixtures used in this investigation are given in the following tables. It will be noticed that the concentration of hydrochloric acid was never less than 0.075N. Sodium tungstate reacts with hydrochloric acid to form a sol according to the equation,

In our experiments, therefore, the molar concentration of tungstate was always less than two-thirds the concentration of hydrochloric acid. The reaction mixtures were quite stable in the dark and no visible turbidity due to the coagulation of the tungstic acid sol occurred during the time of carrying out the experiments.

Kingzett's method was adopted for the titration of hydrogen peroxide left over. About 2 grams of potassium iodide were dissolved in 200 c.c. of water and 30 c.c. of H_2SO_4 solution (1:2) added. 2 C.c. of the reaction mixture were taken out, added to this solution, the flask shaken for five minutes, and the amount of iodine liberated titrated with thiosulphate solution. In acid solution the presence of glucose does not affect the titration in the least.

It was necessary also to determine if the hydrogen peroxide undergoing decomposition is used up entirely for the oxidation of glucose, or whether, a part of the hydrogen peroxide decomposes giving rise to free oxygen which escapes in the atmosphere.

Hence attempts were made to ascertain the amount of glucose left over after the completion of each experiment, and compare the amount of glucose oxidised with the amount of hydrogen peroxide decomposed. The method adopted for glucose estimation was the hypoiodite method of Willstätter (*Ber.*, 1918, 51, 780). The tungstic acid present in the reaction mixture was at first removed by precipitation with barium chloride in approximately neutral solutions. Excess of iodine was then added to the mixture containing glucose and then an equivalent amount of caustic soda solution was added drop by drop to the mixture which was shaken all along. The mixture was then made acidic and the amount of iodine left over was titrated with thiosulphate solution. The alkalinity of the solution during this operation should always be so carefully adjusted that hydrogen peroxide should not undergo spontaneous decomposition with measurable velocity. It may be stated here that oxidation of one molecule of glucose corresponded to the decomposition of one molecule of hydrogen peroxide.

TABLE I.

Composition of the reaction mixture :—

HCl = 0.075 N ; Glucose = 0.025 N ; Sodium tungstate = 0.025 M.

Hydrogen peroxide (Merck's Perhydrol) = 0.0166 M.

Temperature—30.5° ; Spectral region, 330—400 $\mu\mu$.

Time in minutes.	C.c. of thiosulphate \equiv 2 c.c. of reaction mixture.	K (unimolecular with respect to H_2O_2).
1. 0	5.9	0.0024 (from 1 & 2)
2. 60	4.35	0.0041 (from 2 & 3)
3. 120	2.45	0.0041 (from 2 & 4)
4. 180	1.4	

It will be noticed that there is an induction period at the beginning, but after an hour of exposure, the monomolecular velocity constants with respect to hydrogen peroxide agree very well among themselves.

TABLE II.

Effect of change in the concentration of free hydrochloric acid on the monomolecular velocity constant.

Concentrations of glucose and hydrogen peroxide same as in Table I ; temp. 30.5° ; light same as before.

Conc. of total HCl.	Conc. of free HCl.	Conc. of Na-tungstate.	K.
.075 N	.037 N	.025 M	.0041
.108 N	.071 N	.025 M	.0026
.216 N	.180 N	.025 M	.0017
.108 N	.089 N	.0125 M	.0061
.216 N	.197 N	.0125 M	.0040

It will be seen that roughly speaking for the same concentration of tungstic acid, the velocity constants vary inversely as the square root of the concentration of free hydrochloric acid.

TABLE III.

Effect of varying the concentration of sodium tungstate on the velocity of reaction.

Temperature, light intensity, concentrations of glucose and hydrogen peroxide same as in Table I.

Conc. of Na-tungstate	.025 M	.0125 M	.0063 M	.0036 M
Conc. of HCl	.216 N	.216 N	.216 N	.216 N
K (velocity constant)	.0017	.0040	.0055	.0041

The values of the monomolecular constant pass through a maximum as the concentration of sodium tungstate increases.

TABLE IV.

Effect of varying the concentration of glucose on the velocity of reaction.

Temperature, light intensity, concentrations of sodium tungstate, hydrochloric acid, and hydrogen peroxide same as in Table I.

Conc. of glucose025 M	.0125 M	.0063 M
K6041	.0040	.0038

The values of K slightly increase as the concentration of glucose increases. In fact $1/K$ when plotted against the inverse of the concentration of glucose gives a fairly good straight line (*vide* Fig. 1).

Fig. 1.

TABLE V.

Temperature coefficient of K.

Light intensity and composition of reaction mixture same as in Table I

Temp.	30°5	40°5
K	'0041	'0058

The value of K increases 1.3 times for a rise in temperature of ten degrees centigrade.

Discussion of Results.

Any mechanism of reaction, which may be proposed for this photochemical oxidation, should be in a position to explain the following facts:—

1. The velocity of reaction with reference to hydrogen peroxide is monomolecular.
2. The velocity constant is, within a certain range, inversely proportional to the concentration of hydrogen ion.
3. The velocity constant is affected to a very small extent by the concentration of glucose.
4. Other conditions remaining the same, the monomolecular velocity constant at first increases with increase in the concentration of sodium tungstate, passes through a maximum and then diminishes rapidly.

It is well known that the particles of a tungstic acid sol are negatively charged and hydrogen ions therefore will be electrically

absorbed on the surface. According to Mukherjee (*Trans. Farad. Soc.*, 1921, 16, 103), the fraction θ of the original charge on the surface not neutralised by adsorption of monovalent ions is given by the equation $KC\theta^2 + \theta - 1 = 0$, where C is the concentration of the monovalent ion. Now if θ be small compared with unity i.e., if the neutralisation of the charge is almost complete, which we may expect when the concentration of the hydrogen ion is not too small,

$$\theta^2 = \frac{1}{KC} \text{ or } \theta = \frac{K_1}{\sqrt{C_H}}$$

If θ is the fraction of the charge not neutralised by hydrogen ions, it follows that θ also represents the fraction of the total surface of the sol particles which remain available for adsorption by other molecular species. The two molecular species which can conceivably get adsorbed on the surface of the sol particles are glucose and hydrogen peroxide. Now it is well known that hydrogen peroxide has great affinity for tungstic acid. Thus it combines with tungstates to form pertungstates, and Pissarjewsky has actually shown from determination of the distribution of hydrogen peroxide between ether and an aqueous solution of sodium tungstate and sulphuric acid that a considerable fraction of hydrogen peroxide in aqueous solution remains combined with tungstic acid (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1903, 43, 166).

It is evident therefore that on the surface of the particles of tungstic acid sol, not already covered with hydrogen ion, the molecules of hydrogen peroxide will get adsorbed to form a peroxide complex. The amount of complex so formed will be proportional to the concentration of hydrogen peroxide and the free surface θ , or

$$\theta_1 \left(\begin{array}{l} \text{Fraction of surface} \\ \text{covered with molecules of} \\ \text{hydrogen peroxide.} \end{array} \right) = K_2 C_{(H_2O_2)} \cdot \frac{K_1}{\sqrt{C_H}}$$

The elementary spaces of the peroxide surface get activated under the stimulus of radiation and may oxidise a molecule of glucose which happen to collide against this surface during its life period of excitation. If τ be the life period of the excited peroxide space and T be the interval between two successive collisions of glucose molecules on the same peroxide space, the velocity of oxidation of glucose will be given by the equation,

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = K_3 \frac{\tau}{T + \tau} \cdot \theta_1 \text{ (the intensity of effective radiation remaining constant).}$$

T , the interval between two successive collisions of the glucose molecule against the peroxide surface will be inversely proportional to the concentration of glucose.

Hence

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = \frac{\tau}{\frac{A}{C_{\text{(Glucose)}}} + \tau} \cdot K_3 \cdot K_2 \cdot K_1 \cdot \frac{C_{\text{(H}_2\text{O}_2)}}{\sqrt{C_{\text{H}}}}$$

If T or $\frac{A}{C_{\text{(Glucose)}}}$ be small compared with τ , $\frac{dx}{dt} = K_4 \cdot \frac{C_{\text{(H}_2\text{O}_2)}}{\sqrt{C_{\text{H}}}}$ and this is the relation that has been found to hold good in actual experiment. It will also be noticed that the function $\frac{\tau}{\frac{A}{C_{\text{Glucose}}} + \tau}$ is included in the value of K_4 , and $1/K_4$ will therefore include the

function $\frac{\tau + \frac{A}{C_{\text{(Glucose)}}}}{\tau}$

or $1 + \frac{A}{\tau} \cdot \frac{1}{C_{\text{(Glucose)}}}$.

The value of $1/K_4$ when plotted against the inverse of the concentration of glucose should give a straight line which has also been experimentally realised.

The increase in the value of velocity constant with increase in the concentration of the tungstic acid sol to a maximum and then its rapid diminution as the concentration of the photocatalyst is continuously increased, must await a satisfactory explanation until further investigations in progress are carried out. It may be noted however, that in previous communications from this laboratory on the photochemical transformation of *allo*-cinnamylidene-acetic acid into the normal variety, with iodine as photo-catalyst, a similar variation of velocity constant was noticed and the analogy of this phenomenon with the variation of fluorescent intensity as the concentration of the fluorescing substance is increased was brought out.